

FAST SIMULATION OF DEVS MODELS USING THE SIMGRID FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

The Discrete Event System Specification (DEVS) is a formalism widely used to model complex and dynamic systems through an abstraction of discrete events. Currently, there are different simulators that can be used to run models developed in DEVS. The main problem with the existing simulators is the execution time required to run the simulations. This paper proposes a new methodology to describe and define DEVS formalisms in SimGrid. SimGrid is a simulation framework specially designed to simulate distributed systems. Models developed in Simgrid executes in share-memory computers and does not require distributed simulations to obtain good performance. Therefore, the main goal of this paper is to provide a tool for executing fast simulations of DEVS models.

Keywords: DEVS, Simulator, Events, SimGrid, JSON.

1 DESCRIPTION OF THE METHODOLOGY

In order to explain the modeling process, the steps that have been carried out will be detailed. Finally, a use case will be briefly shown, comparing the results obtained with another existing DEVS simulator, called PythonPDEVS (Van Tendeloo and Vangheluwe 2014, Song et al. 2006). First, thanks to the graphical tool XFD-DEVS (Mittal et al. 2007), a DEVS model is defined and exported in XML format. In this graphical tool we have defined the states, the execution times and the connections, both internal transitions and external transitions due to external events.

After having the XML file generated, a conversion to JSON format is performed, since it is a text format widely used in other tools and easy to understand. Once the JSON format file describing the model is obtained, a translation of the DEVS entities will be made to the SimGrid (Casanova, Henri 2021) simulation tool, which allows simulations with a large number of elements without the need to perform distributed simulations, since it is characterized by its efficiency and good use of memory.

Starting from the model in JSON format, several scripts developed in Python are used to convert them into a series of C files for their correct execution in SimGrid, in addition to an XML file that defines the topology to be built by the simulator.

The first step to generate these C files is to know how to translate the DEVS entities to SimGrid. The most important entity is the DEVS states that in SimGrid will behave as processes that have a mailbox associated with them waiting to receive a message to continue their execution. In addition, each state will wait for a

Figure 1: DEVS model graph

Figure 2: Real Simulator Runtime

certain time after receiving it before moving to the next state. In addition, to define the internal transition functions, the JSON file itself defines which will be the next state to be executed during the simulation, while for the external transitions, there is an extra process that will communicate with the states to send a different message that determines the change to a different state from the expected one.

Having explained the most important details of this methodology, which is in its early stages as we are using third party tools to generate the models, it is convenient to show a very simple example of a traffic light that changes its color for a certain amount of time (carried out by Van Tendeloo and Vangheluwe (2017)), until it receives a message that makes the traffic light turn off for a random amount of time. In addition, this test case has also been used in the PythonPDEVS tool to compare performance with SimGrid (Figures 1 and 2).

2 CONCLUSIONS

The methodology developed and explained in this paper allows to define DEVS models using the abstractions defined in the SimGrid simulation toolkit. This definition allows to execute DEVS simulations in an efficient way in shared memory computers.

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